

Adventures in globally unique identifiers at the Smithsonian

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ID2) Identifiers and labels in natural history collections: new technologies, challenges and opportunities for linking objects and data, Lecture Theatre 1, Appleton Tower, 11 Crichton Street, EH8 9LE, June 7, 2022, 4:00 PM - 5:30 PM

In early 2020, the Smithsonian used our Open Access initiative as a driver to introduce an institution wide approach to persistent and globally unique identifiers, building on the existing implementations at the National Museum of Natural History (NMNH) and Smithsonian Libraries and Archives (SLA). Our solution had to simultaneously:

- work across multiple domains from collections, to library and archives, to art and humanities
- be applied to legacy and new datasets
- be automated within all the various databases, infrastructure, workflows, and data sharing already in place

This talk will outline the reasoning behind key decisions, provide lessons learned and pitfalls to look out for, as well as what having these identifiers in place enables NMNH and the Smithsonian to do going forward.

